

Determination of the effect of antenatal care on newborn birth weight

Determinación del efecto de la atención prenatal en el peso al nacer del recién nacido

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Abstract

Background and Objectives: The World Health Organization (WHO) executed diverse antenatal care concepts to optimize maternal and child outcomes. In resource-constrained nations, the conventional style entailing meetings every four weeks till the 28 weeks, after which biweekly till 36 weeks, and each week till delivery, was complex. The immediate purpose of antenatal care is to ensure that the mother and baby have the best probable health results. The study's primary objective is to determine the effect of antenatal care on newborn birth weight. **Methodology:** This current study was a cross-sectional study that lasted 30 days, from April 4th to May 5th, 2021. An interview questionnaire is employed as a research instrument to achieve the purposes of this research. This study's sample comprises 150 women who are patients at Bint Al-Huda Hospital in Al-Nasiriyah City. **Results:** The findings of children's births were based on weight, with the vast bulk of births weighing just under the standard. Whereas women visited the hospital for pregnant women follow-up, the majority of participants were unsatisfied with the hospital's care, with a significant proportion exceeding the majority of the sample. **Conclusion:** Cesarean delivery was the most typical among respondents. The arranging of the children was the second baby. In contrast, the gestational age of women has been more than 40 weeks was the most common in the study population. Adherence to antenatal care, or at least four visits, will decrease the occurrence of birth weight.

Keywords: Antenatal Care, Birth Weight, Newborn, Health Results.

Resumen

Antecedentes y objetivos: La Organización Mundial de la Salud (OMS) ejecutó diversos conceptos de atención prenatal para optimizar los resultados maternos e infantiles. En países con recursos limitados, el estilo convencional que implicaba reuniones cada cuatro semanas hasta las 28 semanas, luego cada dos semanas hasta las 36 semanas y cada semana hasta el parto, era complejo. El propósito inmediato de la atención prenatal es asegurar que la madre y el bebé tengan los mejores resultados de salud probables. El objetivo principal del estudio es determinar el efecto de la atención prenatal en el peso al nacer del recién nacido. **Metodología:** El presente estudio fue un estudio transversal que tuvo una duración de 30 días, del 4 de abril al 5 de mayo de 2021. Se emplea como instrumento de investigación un cuestionario de entrevista para lograr los propósitos de esta investigación. La muestra de este estudio comprende 150 mujeres que son pacientes en el Hospital Bint Al-Huda en la ciudad de Al-Nasiriyah. **Resultados:** Los resultados de los nacimientos de niños se basaron en el peso, y la gran mayoría de los nacimientos pesaban justo por debajo del estándar. Mientras que las mujeres acudían al hospital para el seguimiento de las embarazadas, la mayoría de las participantes estaba insatisfecha con la atención del hospital, con una proporción significativa que superaba a la mayoría de la muestra. **Conclusión:** El parto por cesárea fue el más habitual entre los encuestados. El arreglo de los niños fue el segundo bebé. En cambio, la edad gestacional de las mujeres ha sido mayor a 40 semanas fue la más común en la población de estudio. La adherencia a la atención prenatal, o al menos cuatro visitas, disminuirá la incidencia de peso al nacer.

Palabras clave: Atención prenatal, peso al nacer, recién nacido, resultados en salud.

Antenatal care is a specific style of care designed for expectant mothers to help them achieve as well as promote a healthier life all across their pregnancy, increasing their likelihood of acquiring a safe delivery of a good health infant¹. The primary goal of antenatal care is to guarantee that the mother and her

baby have the best possible health results². It consists of a sequence of counseling sessions as well as follow up provided by a specific healthcare professional (doctors, midwives, and trained auxiliary nurses) with the goal of observing pregnancy as well as fetal development, early diagnosis of health problems and therapeutic interventions, and disease prevention across vaccination as well as nutritional supplementation^{3,4}. Also it makes sure birth preparations and complication preparedness, as well as overall health advancement for pregnant women, across public health interventions and consultation⁵. Across a 15-year period, the World Health Organization (WHO) implemented various antenatal care concepts in attempt to optimize maternal and child results. In resource-constrained nations, the conventional system, which entails a sequence of visits every 4 weeks till 28 weeks, after which biweekly till 36 weeks, and each week till delivery, was difficult. The centered antenatal care concept, which includes lesser (4) visits and concentrates on quality of healthcare rather than quantity, was introduced in 2001^{6,7}. Due to financial constraints, four visits were suggested for third world countries. Nevertheless, reducing the frequency of visits did not resolve the issue of lowered perinatal and maternal deaths, adverse pregnancy outcomes, as well as decreased satisfaction with the lowered visit. New According to WHO standards, 8 visits rather than four throughout pregnancy give a larger opportunities to contact with a health professional, raise the opportunity of diagnosing health problems, perform precautionary measures, and communicate better among a pregnant woman and her healthcare professional. It advises visits as the first point of contact during first 12 weeks, followed by visits at 20, 26, 30, 34, 36, 38, and 40 weeks of gestation^{7,8}. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), prenatal care comprises of 4 visits by expectant mothers to medical centers as well as medical experts. The 4 antenatal care services ensure necessary nutrients, micronutrient intake, immunization, workout, deleterious behavioral interventions, and organizational delivery. Pregnancy is among the most vulnerable times in a woman's life, respectively physically and mentally⁹. Excellent prenatal care is essential for the mother's health and the growth of the unborn child. Medications are necessary throughout pregnancy for healthy habits and care and mothering abilities. Antenatal care is a concept that applies to all medical interventions and

care provided throughout pregnancy. When it comes to improving antenatal care, it is critical that the efficiency of this delivery is unmistakable¹⁰. Prenatal care is an important approach for increasing community health goals, primary care objectives, and the Millennium Development agenda¹¹.

Study design

The research is a cross analysis that lasted 30 days, from April 4 to May 5, 2021. A structured interview is used as a study instrument to obtain the study's objectives.

Setting of the study

An effect of antenatal care on Birth Weight of Newborn in Bint Al-Huda Hospital at Al-Nasiriyah City

Data analysis

The data was gathered using a person being interviewed questionnaire, and the information was analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23. (SPSS). To make a comparison distinctions among categorical data, chi square tests have been used. P 5% (0.05) is used to determine statistical significance.

Ethical consideration

Ethical clearance was gathered for the research from the Research and Ethics Committee, Bint Al-Huda Hospital at Al-Nasiriyah City, Iraq. The approval date is March 14, 2021.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of the Variables Mothers' (n=150)

Socio demographic	Scale	NO.	%
Age	≤20	17	11.3
	21-25	47	31.3
	26-30	35	23.3
	more than 30	51	34.0
	SD =2.801.03		
Level of education	not read & not write	15	10.0
	Elementary	33	22.0
	Secondary	12	8.0
	High school	53	35.3
	Graduation & above	37	24.7
Type of place of residence	Urban	98	65.3
	Suburban	52	34.6
Occupation	Housewife	103	68.7
	employee	47	31.3
Type of delivery	C/S	97	64.6
	Normal	53	35.3
Birth order	First child	35	23.3
	Second and more	115	76.6
Gestational age during delivery (weeks)	≥ 40	15	10
	< 40	135	90

= Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, %= percentage, NO.= Number

Table 1 indicated according to the results, The participants' ages ranged from lesser than 20 to and over 30 years, with the mean age becoming 2.80 (standard deviation [SD] 1.03) years. The age group (and over 30) (34.0 percent) was the large percentage within that research. In terms of residence, the majority of women (65.3 percent) in the study sample lived in cities. In regarding education, the majority of individuals had a high school, accounting for approximately (35.3 percent) of the research. In terms of occupation, nearly (68.7 percent) of the research participants were housewives. With regard to the mode of delivery, the bulk of participants (64.6 percent) of the sample population were C/S. In terms of birth order, the majority of the participants was the second child and more (76.6 percent). In terms of gestational age at delivery (weeks), the majority of participants were more than 40 weeks pregnant (90 percent).

Table 2. Results of Percentage Birth weight Data

Baby's Weight was born	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
≥ 2500 kg	93	62.0
≤ 2500 kg	57	38.0
Total	150	100

F= Frequency, % = Percentage, kg = kilogram

Table 2 has shown that the proportion of birth weight just under 2500 kg were the majority of the research study (62.0 percent), whereas the proportion of birth weight greater than 2500 kg were approximately (38.0 percent) of the research study.

Table 3. The Percentage Results of Antenatal Care Data

ANC visit	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Fulfilled	43	28.6
Not fulfilled	107	71.3
Total	150	100

ANC = Antenatal Care, F= Frequency, % = Percentage

Table 3 revealed according to the proportion findings of ante-natal care information, the large number of the population (71.3 percent) have not been accomplished in their visits, whereas there was (28.6 percent) have been accomplished in their visits to antenatal care.

Table 4. Relations of Birth Weight and Antenatal Care

		ANC compliance	BW
ANC compliance	Correlation coefficient	1.000	0.013*
	Sig. (2-tailed) N	- 26112	0.036 26112
BW	Correlation coefficient	0.013*	1.000
	Sig. (2-tailed) N	0.036 26112	. 26112

ANC = Antenatal Care, BW= Birth Weight

The association between the independent variable and the dependent variable was evaluated utilizing chi-square and P 0.05 was gained, indicating that there is a significant relation among antenatal care adherence and birth weight occurrence. This means that adherence to antenatal care or at least 4 visits will contribute to the reduction of birth weight. The direction of the relationship using Spearman's rho correlations has shown that the coefficient number between the ante-natal care and birth weight compliance variables is positive at 0.036, indicating that the correlation between the two variables is unidirectional. As a result, if the antenatal care adherence score is good, the birth weight will be good.

Discussion

Discussion of descriptive statistics of the mothers' variables:

The respondents' ages ranged with less than 20 to and over 30 years, with the mean age to be 2.80 (standard deviation [SD] 1.03) years. The age category (over than 30) (34.0 percent) was the large percentage throughout this research. In terms of residence, the majority of women (65.3 percent) in the research study were lived in cities. In areas of education, the majority of individuals had a high school, accounting for approximately (35.3 percent) of the sample. In terms of occupation, roughly (68.7 percent) of the research participants were housewives. With regard to the mode of delivery, the majority of the participants (64.6 percent) were delivered via C/S. In terms of birth order, the majority of the sample was the second child as well as more (76.6 percent). In terms of gestational age at delivery (weeks), the majority of respondents seem to be more than 40 (90 percent). These results come consistent with Celik & Younis (2007)¹² who demonstrated that such age group of women has been more over thirty years old, where it reflected (33.6 percent) the bulk of the research, as well as the large percent of the participants living in cities (66.5 percent) of the sample population, and the woman's most recent birth was her second or higher birth (58.5 percent of woman). These results supported by Adamou, Abdul & Umar (2020)¹³ who mentioned that 46 (50%) of participants seemed to have tertiary education whereas 2 (2.2%) were uneducated. In addition, 55 (59.8 percent) of women have been economically inactive (housewife).

Discussion of results of percentage birth weight data:

The proportion of birth weight just under 2500 kg comprised approximately 62.0 percent of the study sample, whereas the proportion of birth weight greater than 2500 kg comprised approximately 38.0 percent of the study sample. These results come along with Zhou et al. (2019)¹⁴ The findings showed that nearly 9.3 percent of babies born in the study region had such a low birth

weight (LBW). Since controlling for other effects, insufficient antenatal care (ANC) meetings as well as an absence about certain antenatal care services were known to be correlated with LBW in a multilevel concept. Nevertheless, antenatal care coverage, ease of access, as well as care effectiveness remain low in Western China's current impoverished country places.

Discussion the percentage results of antenatal care data:

The proportion of the respondents (71.3 percent) were not satisfied with their visits; however, there were (28.6 percent) who were satisfied with their visits to ante-natal care. This results agree with Andersson, Christensson & Hildingsson (2013)¹⁵ who mentioned that the main results of this research were that women showed substantial inadequacies in their antenatal services in both care models. These results come inconsistent with Hildingsson et al. (2013)¹⁶ who reported that both groups of women were pleased with their antenatal services. Australian women were more pleased well with sentimental aspects of patient care than Swedish women. And over half of the factors pertaining to particular areas of care were found to be deficient. Inadequate knowledge and not being treated seriously were major reasons for dissatisfaction.

Discussion of relations of birth weight and antenatal care:

The association in between independent variable and the dependent variable was evaluated utilizing chi-square and P 0.05 was acquired, indicating that there is indeed a significant relation among antenatal care adherence and birth weight occurrence. This means that adherence to antenatal care or to at least 4 visits will reduce the prevalence of low birth weight. These results come along with Zhou et al. (2019)¹⁴ who observed that the sufficiency of antenatal care components (including the amount of antenatal care visits approximated for gestational age, wholeness of treatment, or the value of prenatal assessments) was linked to low birth weight and a variety of other pregnancy complications. These results supported by Pinzón-Rondón et al.(2015)¹⁷ who revealed that the percentage of prenatal visits and gestational age at the first antenatal visit were both important predictors against low birth weight in both the unadjusted and adjusted concepts.

Conclusions

The average age of the participants was 2.80; women's ages ranged towards less than 20 to and over thirty years; the predominate age category has been more than 30 years. The majority of the respondents have been housewives living in urban areas with a high school degree, whereas cesarean delivery has been the most common amongst respondents and the adjustment of the children was the second child, whereas the gestational age of women has been more than 40 weeks was the most in the study population. The findings of children's births were based on weight, with the vast bulk of births weighing just under standard. Whereas women visited the hospital for pregnant women follow-up, the majority of participants were unsatisfied with the hospital's care, with a significant proportion exceeding the majority of the sample. Be satisfied with the services offered, even if it is a minority. There was a meaningful correlation among antenatal care and births of children weighing less than the normal weight (P 0.05).

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